

THE EXPANDED SERIES OF MULTIPLE HARMONIC SUMS AND MULTIPLE ZETA VALUES

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March 5, 2023

Abstract

In this paper, we introduce an explicit expanded series for multiple zeta values. The series is rapidly convergent and defined in a wide region. Additionally, the series yields innumerable identities.

1 Notation

1. Define multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{1 \leq k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

In the same way, define finite multiple zeta value as

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &:= \sum_{1 \leq k_m < k_{m-1} < \dots < k_1 \leq q} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}} \\ &= \sum_{k_m=1}^q \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^q \dots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_1} k_2^{\alpha_2} \dots k_m^{\alpha_m}}.\end{aligned}$$

And, $\zeta_q(\alpha_k, \dots, \alpha_{k-1}) := 1$.

2. $\{\alpha\}^m := \underbrace{(\alpha, \dots, \alpha)}_m$.

3. Define difference operator as

$$\Delta_q[f(q)] := f(q+1) - f(q).$$

4. $S_{1st} \binom{\alpha}{\beta}$ denotes the unsigned stirling number of the first kind.

2 The Expansion Formula

Theorem 2.1. *with $\text{Re}(\alpha_1) > 1$ and $q \notin \mathbb{Z}_{<0}$, it follows;*

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q + k + \alpha_1 - 1)!},$$

$$\text{where } \forall x, \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{x!}{(x+k+\alpha_1)!} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(x+1)^{\alpha_j-1} (k+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{x!}{(x+k+\alpha_1)!} \quad (2 \leq j \leq m),$$

$$A_{2,k} = S_{1st} \binom{k + \alpha_1 - 1}{\alpha_1 - 1}.$$

Proof. Calculating both sides with difference operator will prove that. First, the left side is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_q[\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] &= -\Delta_q[\zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] \\
&= -\sum_{k_m=1}^{q+1} \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^{q+1} \cdots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^{q+1} \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_m} k_2^{\alpha_{m-1}} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_1}} \\
&\quad + \sum_{k_m=1}^q \sum_{k_{m-1}=k_m+1}^q \cdots \sum_{k_1=k_2+1}^q \frac{1}{k_1^{\alpha_m} k_2^{\alpha_{m-1}} \cdots k_m^{\alpha_1}} \\
&= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}}. \tag{1}
\end{aligned}$$

Second, the right side is,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \right] \\
&= -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&= -\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m) S_{1st} \left(\begin{matrix} k + \alpha_1 - 1 \\ \alpha_1 - 1 \end{matrix} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&\quad - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \\
&= -\frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m)}{(q+1)^{\alpha_1}} - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^m \left(A_{j+1,k} - \frac{A_{j,k}}{(k+\alpha_1-1)(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1}} \right) \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!}. \tag{2}
\end{aligned}$$

Comparing (1) and (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \\
\Leftrightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_{j+1,k} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A_{j,k}}{(q+1)^{\alpha_j-1} (k+\alpha_1-1)} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1)!} \quad (2 \leq j \leq m), \\
A_{2,k} &= S_{1st} \left(\begin{matrix} k + \alpha_1 - 1 \\ \alpha_1 - 1 \end{matrix} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore we have

$$\Delta_q [\zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)] = \Delta_q \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} \right] \tag{3}$$

and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \zeta(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m) = \lim_{q \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{j=2}^{m+1} \frac{A_{j,k} \zeta_q(\alpha_j, \dots, \alpha_m)}{k + \alpha_1 - 1} \frac{q!}{(q+k+\alpha_1-1)!} = 0. \tag{4}$$

The theorem follows from (3) and (4). □

The expansion formula can be applied for many uses. We have a few examples;

Example 2.1. with $1 < \alpha$,

$$\zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \left(\begin{matrix} k + \alpha - 1 \\ \alpha - 1 \end{matrix} \right)}{(k + \alpha - 1)^{m+1} (k + \alpha - 1)!}.$$

Proof. In theorem 2.1, let $(q, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{m+1}) \rightarrow (1, \alpha, 1, \dots, 1)$. □

We can see this equation as an analytic continuation for $\zeta(\alpha, \{1\}^m)$. For example,

Example 2.2.

$$\zeta(2, \{1\}^m) = \zeta(m+2).$$

Example 2.3. with $1 < \alpha_1$,

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_q(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{\zeta_q(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \frac{(\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_k(\alpha_1)) - (\zeta(\alpha_1) - \zeta_q(\alpha_1))}{k^{\alpha_2}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^q \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \left(\frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!} - \frac{q!}{(q + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Let $q \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\zeta(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{S_{1st} \binom{j+\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1-1}}{k^{\alpha_2} (j + \alpha_1 - 1)} \frac{k!}{(k + j + \alpha_1 - 1)!}.$$

□

For instance,

Example 2.4.

$$\zeta(3) = \zeta(2, 1) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(k-1)!(j-1)!}{j(k+j)!}.$$

Example 2.5.

$$\frac{3}{4}\zeta(4) = \zeta(2, 2) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(k-1)!(j-1)!}{jk(k+j)!}.$$

References

- [1] Hanamichi Kawamura, Takumi Maesaka, Shin-ichiro Seki *Multivariable connected sums and multiple polylogarithms.* [arXiv](#)

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